

THE MEDIATING EFFECT OF ATTITUDE TOWARD MATHEMATICS BETWEEN ONLINE LEARNING READINESS AND SATISFACTION

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The Mediating Effect of Attitude toward Mathematics between Online Learning Readiness and Satisfaction

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Abstract

Online learning is perceived differently by students than face-to-face or traditional learning. Because the pandemic has sickened many people, students can still attend school whenever they want. Online math classes are less popular with students who aren't ready to learn in a new way. This study examined whether math attitudes affect online learning readiness. The study looked at 153 STEM high school students' performance in an entirely online math class. We used self-reporting tools like the OLSRS, ATMI, and the online learning satisfactory scale to gather data (OLSS). According to OLS regression-based path analysis and simple mediation analysis, students who were ready to learn math online were satisfied with the subject mathematics. An online learner has a positive attitude towards math, which leads to a high level of satisfaction. Also, math attitudes were found to be a "mediator" between online learning reading and math satisfaction.

Keywords: *online learning, readiness, attitude towards mathematics, satisfaction, STEM*

Introduction

The Internet, particularly in education, is one of the essential technologies in almost every human life field that has been successfully used (Horzum, 2017). As a result of network technology developments and an increase in current technological devices' capacity to deliver learning (Watkins et al., 2008), online learning practices have gained momentum (Firat & Bozkurt, 2020). Internet is a complete learning environment for distance education and supports face-to-face learning (Horzum et al., 2015). Online learning stands out among distance education applications through the Internet. The Internet offers access to, acquiring theoretical knowledge, and exploring and applying knowledge to intercultural and customized learning (Demir et al., 2013; Holmes & Gardner, 2006).

Online learning opportunities and benefits are two of the main reasons people use it all the time and all over the place. In the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic (Panattil et al., 1 C.E.), a lot of educational institutions are moving to distance online learning, where there will be no more face-to-face meetings in class. They will instead offer lessons and coursework online. Online learning has a lot of good things going for it, like that it's all about the students and lets them study when they want (Horzum et al., 2015; Simonson et al., 2000). It can be used for communication and interaction, either synchronously or asynchronously (Demir et al., 2013).

Online learning is very different from how many students in the Philippines used to learn in the past. In distance education, students' readiness for this type of learning environment affects their attendance and dropout rate (Demir et al., 2013). Garris et al., 2002; Kwangsu & Kyeongyong, 2005; Kim & Lee, 2011). It is important to know which factors make learners happy with their learning and learning flow in order to make online learning a success, especially in math.

The challenges of learning mathematics today with fully online learning are self-controlled study, concentration, and motivation. The Mathematics subjects are comprised of solving problems, reasoning, mathematical issues, making interpretations, and concepts that students' demands are highly motivated (Ergogo, 2012). Positive attitudes toward mathematics are indicative of a favorable emotional disposition toward the subject, and vice versa (Zan & Di Martino, 2007). Thus, positive mathematics attitudes are important since they may impact learning motivation and the benefits of mathematical instruction (Eshun, 2006).

This study aimed to determine whether students' attitudes toward mathematics mediate the connection between online learning readiness and satisfaction in mathematics.

Literature Review

Students satisfaction is another important measure in online distance learning. Due to its importance in a learning activity, academics have long studied student satisfaction. Many teachers ask students for feedback at the end of class (Rafsanjani et al., 2021). Online learning satisfaction has only recently been measured in the COVID-19 pandemic. Many studies on student learning satisfaction exist. The level of satisfaction is simply the students' compatibility with the emergency Covid-19 online learning system (Coman et al., 2020). Some students find online teaching quite satisfactory (Cole et al., 2014; Harahap et al., 2021). This means that the positive response of both students and teachers to online learning is a wise attitude that every student or anyone must have in order to support the development of hybrid learning, and there is a match between the service's expectations and its actual performance (Harahap et al., 2021; Prasetio et al., 2017).

Student satisfaction in an online learning environment is a multifaceted and intricate construct (Dziuban et al., 2015; Wei & Chou, 2020; Yilmaz, 2017). In general, student satisfaction refers to the student's happiness and satisfaction with the various aspects of the service received. In general, student satisfaction refers to the student's happiness and satisfaction with the various aspects of the service

received (Karatas & Simsek, 2009; Yilmaz, 2017). In addition, satisfaction is a construct directly derived from service components (Wei & Chou, 2020). When attending online learning, students will personally assess whether they are satisfied or dissatisfied with the learning process that they are going through (Robbins & Judge, 2007). Students experience learning satisfaction when they perceive a connection between expectation and experience (Rizki Mulyani et al., 2019). In other words, students who are happy with their learning activities will be ready to learn online. Students feel satisfied when their expectations are met or exceeded (Rizki Mulyani et al., 2019; Chang & Chang, 2012).

Additional research has examined satisfaction with the quality of online interactions. For example, Felix (2001) found that students had a negative attitude towards online learning when there was inadequate personal interaction. Attitude is a commonly used term in the mathematics education literature as well, yet it is a concept difficult to define precisely (Can et al., 2017). In fact, according to Tobias (1995), the term has been used interchangeably with others such as mathematics anxiety, which actually refers to feelings of tension interfering with the individual's ability to solve mathematical problems in different academic contexts (Can et al., 2017).

As online learning continues to expand in anticipation of the COVID-19 pandemic, online learning environments permit students to plan and direct their own learning (Muasyaroh & Royanto, 2021). Student's readiness is an imperative factor for participation in learning (Lau, 2008). It was suggested that one of the eight principles of learning is readiness (Lau, 2012, 2008; Moss, 1987) and students will learn better if they are ready to learn. Studies have shown a significant and positive correlation between online learning readiness and the students' attitudes towards the subject (Bovermann et al., 2018; Hergüner et al., 2020). The learner who has a high level of readiness can comment on the topic and do assignments more easily by comprehending the subjects sooner; on learning the previous topic thoroughly, he/she could be ready to move on to the next one (Harman & Çelikler, 2012; Topal, 2016). The process of determining a learner's readiness for this method of instruction benefits both the learner and the instructor. In order to ensure the success of online distance learning, it is critical to assess the effect of students' readiness level on satisfaction (Topal, 2016).

It is critical to conduct extensive research into the elements and factors that contribute to student satisfaction with online education. As stated previously, this study hypothesizes that online learning readiness and attitude toward mathematics directly affect online learning satisfaction, both directly and indirectly via the use of attitudes as an intervening variable. The following is a description of the path analysis used in the study:

Fig. 1. Proposed model for online learning readiness, attitude toward mathematics, and online learning satisfaction

Methodology

Research Design

A correlational research design was conducted utilizing the ordinary least squares (OLS) regression-based path analysis and simple mediation analysis. OLS regression-based path analysis is used to test the effect of the independent variable dependent variable that can be partitioned into two paths of influence; direct and indirect. Simple mediation analysis is a statistical method used to evaluate evidence on how an independent variable transmit its effect on the dependent variable (Hayes, 2018).

Participants

This study's participants were the senior high school students enrolled in STEM strand taking fully online courses in Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College. An online survey was conducted utilizing google forms. The survey form was restricted to students with Gsuites accounts issued by the institution to ensure that the participants are currently enrolled. Due to some students' internet connectivity issues, a sample of 153 responses was obtained and included in our analysis.

Instruments

This study was collected using the online learning readiness scale (OLRS), attitude toward mathematics inventory (ATMI), and online learning satisfaction.

Online Learning Readiness Scale (OLRS)

Online learning readiness was measured using the Online Learning Readiness Scale (OLRS), which contains 18 items developed by Hung et al. (2010). Jena (2016) cited OLRS has five subscales: computer/internet self-efficacy; self-directed learning; learner control; motivation for learning; and online communication self-efficacy. On a 5-point Likert scale, items were rated from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). The Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficients calculated for this study are .729 for the computer/internet self-efficacy subscale, .663 for the self-directed learning subscale, .802 for the learner control subscale, .661 for the motivation for learning subscale, .747 for the online communication self-efficacy subscale. Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient was .856 for the entire online learning readiness scale. The scale represents a high-reliability estimate of internal consistency as it relates to composite scores.

Attitude Toward Mathematics Inventory (ATMI)

Attitudes toward mathematics were measured using the Attitudes Toward Mathematics Inventory (ATMI), consisting of 46 questions measuring four factors affecting students' attitudes developed by Tapia & Marsh (2002). As cited by Cerbito (2020), the four subscales were: self-confidence (15 items), the value of mathematics (10 items), enjoyment in mathematics (10 items), and motivation (5 items). The survey responses were measures from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree(5), positive and negative statements are included. Cronbach alpha reliability coefficients for self-confidence, mathematical value, mathematical enjoyment, and motivation are .420, .720, .726, and .955, respectively. For the overall attitude toward mathematics, the Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient is .791, indicating a high-reliability internal consistency estimate relevant to the composite scores.

Online Learning Satisfaction In Mathematics (OLSM)

Online learning satisfaction was measured using three of the four subscales designed by Lee (2014): satisfaction levels associated with SHS math teacher (4 items), satisfaction level associated with the subject structure (6 items), and satisfaction level associated with technical aspects. The Cronbach alpha reliability coefficients for each subscale are .903 for satisfaction levels associated with SHS math teacher, .938 for satisfaction level associated with the subject structure, and .931 for satisfaction level associated with technical aspects. The Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient for overall satisfaction was .974, indicating an excellent internal consistency reliability estimate relevant to the composite scores.

Data Analysis

The researcher analyzed the data with the help of SPSS statistics 23. First, the researcher performed a Pearson's correlation analysis in order to determine the overall relationships between the variables under consideration (Sedgwick, 2012). The researcher then applied the PROCESS macro (Hayes, 2018) to determine whether attitude toward mathematics had a mediating effect on the relationship between OLR and OLS. The researcher analyzed the data with the help of SPSS statistics 23.

Results and Discussion

Descriptive statistics

Descriptive statistics and correlations for all variables are presented in Table 1. Correlation analysis reveals that online learning readiness was significantly related to attitude towards mathematics ($r=.455, p<.01$) and online learning satisfaction ($r=.175, p<.05$), and that attitude towards mathematics was significantly related to online learning satisfaction ($r=.622, p<.01$).

Table 1. Mean, Standard Deviations, and Intercorrelation of Variables of the Study

	M	SD	1	2	3
1. OLR	3.56	0.44	1		
2. ATM	3.54	0.41	.455**	1	
3. OLSM	4.13	0.90	.175*	.622**	1

Note: N=153; OLR=Online Learning Readiness, ATM=Attitudes Towards Mathematics,

OLSM=Online Learning Satisfaction in Mathematics

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Mediating effects

The researcher conducted the PROCESS macro to test the mediating effect of attitudes toward mathematics (Hayes, 2018). As can be seen in Table 2, the regression models are,

$$\hat{M} = 2.032 + .423X + e_M$$

$$\hat{Y}_{Direct} = -0.187 - 0.278X + 1.501M + e_Y$$

$$\hat{Y}_{total} = 2.687 + 0.3567X + e_Y$$

Table 2. Regression results from simple mediation

Antecedent		Consequent								
		M (ATM)				Y (OLSM)				
		Coeff.	SE	t	p	Coeff.	SE	t	p	
X (OLR)	a	.423	.068	.455	6.274	.000				
M (ATM)										
	b									
Constant	iM	2.032	.242		8.397	.000				
	iy									
R2=.2068					R2=.4015					
F1,151=39.3613, p=.000					F1,151=50.3214, p=.000					
		Boot	SE	Boot LLCI	Boot ULCI					
Bootstrap results for the indirect effect										
Effect		0.635	0.154	.342	.943					

Note: Adapted from Hayes (2018). Introduction to mediation, moderation, and conditional process analysis: A regression-based approach. Guilford publications. Bootstrap sample size=5000. LLCI=lower bound in 95% confidence interval; ULCI=upper bound in 95% confidence interval.

Fig. 2. Proposed model for online learning readiness, attitude toward mathematics, and online learning satisfaction

As shown in Table 2, OLR has a negative effect on OLS (B=0.2784, =.1363), implying that a student who is not yet ready for online learning is estimated to be 0.2784 less satisfied with online learning. However, as can be seen, this effect is not statistically significant, t(151)=-1.9224,p>.05. OLR had a positive effect on ATM (B=0.423,=.455), and this direct effect is statistically significant, t(151)=6.274,p.05, implying that as OLR increases, ATM will become more positive. ATM had a significant positive effect on OLS (B=1.501,=.684,t(151)=9.644,p.05), implying that a positive ATM results in a high OLS level. The total effect of OLR on OLS was significantly increased when the mediator (ATM) was included in the model (B=0.357,=.175,t(151)=2.180 p.05).

Bootstrapping was used to determine whether ATM indirectly affected the relationship between OLR and OLS (Shrout & Bolger, 2002). A non-zero 95 percent bootstrap confidence interval indicated that the indirect effect of OLR on OLS via ATM was statistically significant (B=0.35, SE=0.154, 95 percent CI=[0.342, 0.943]). (Table 2). As a result, we determined that ATM completely mediated the relationship between OLR and OLS. Bootstrapping was used to determine whether ATM indirectly affected the relationship between OLR and OLS (Shrout & Bolger, 2002). A non-zero 95 percent bootstrap confidence interval indicated that the indirect effect of OLR on OLS via ATM was statistically significant (B=0.35, SE=0.154, 95 percent CI=[0.342, 0.943]). (Table 2). As a result, we determined that ATM completely mediated the relationship between OLR and OLS.

Conclusions

As a result of the study, online distance learning during the pandemic was evaluated from students perspectives. The overall research findings found that online learning readiness and attitudes towards mathematics are the factors that influence online learning satisfaction. This study also shows that attitudes towards mathematics learning are indispensable for enhancing online learning satisfaction. Thus, attitudes towards mathematics learning positively affect students online learning satisfaction and mediate the relationship between online learning readiness and satisfaction.

There are several limitations to this study. First, all study variables were self-reported via a questionnaire. Consequently, students could consistently answer questions in one way, inflating the results and measuring online learning satisfaction rather than academic performance. Another design is cross-sectional. The study found a link between online learning readiness, mathematics attitude, and satisfaction, but not causal. More research is needed to determine whether students' attitudes toward mathematics mediate between online learning readiness and satisfaction. (3) All participants were STEM students at one private university. As a result of institutional culture, online learning satisfaction is highly dependent on the specific private institution in an urban area with internet connectivity.

Our findings may not be replicable in other private or public institutions with limited or no internet connectivity. Finally, the instruments for assessing online learning readiness, mathematics attitudes, and satisfaction were adopted. No confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was performed, but the reliability analysis using Cronbach's alpha shows high internal consistency between the items of each measure.

References

- Banahene, S., Kraa, J. J., & Kasu, P. A. (2018). Impact of HEDPERF on students' satisfaction and academic performance in Ghanaian universities; Mediating role of attitude towards learning.
- Bollen, K. A. (1989). *Structural Equations with Latent Variables*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Bovermann, K., Weidlich, J., & Bastiaens, T. (2018). Online learning readiness and attitudes towards gaming in gamified online learning – a mixed methods case study. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 15(1), 27. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-018-0107-0>
- Bovermann, K., Weidlich, J., & Bastiaens, T. (2018). Online learning readiness and attitudes towards gaming in gamified online learning—a mixed methods case study. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 15(1), 1-17.
- Can, I., Koydemir, S., Durhan, S., Ogan, S., Gozukara, C., & Cokluk, G. (2017). Changing High School Students' Attitudes Towards Mathematics in a Summer Camp: Happiness Matters. *Educational Sciences: Theory & Practice*, 17(5), Article 5. <https://doi.org/10.12738/estp.2017.5.0373>
- Cerbito, A. F. (2020). Comparative Analysis of Mathematics Proficiency and Attitudes Toward Mathematics of Senior High School Student. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications (IJSRP)*, 10(05), 211–222. <https://doi.org/10.29322/IJSRP.10.05.2020.p10125>
- Cerin, E., & Mackinnon, D. P. (2009). A commentary on current practice in mediating variable analyses in behavioural nutrition and physical activity. *Public Health Nutrition*, 12(8), 1182–1188. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1368980008003649>
- Cole, M. T., Shelley, D. J., & Swartz, L. B. (2014). Online instruction, e-learning, and student satisfaction: A three year study. *The International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 15(6). <https://doi.org/10.19173/irrodl.v15i6.1748>
- Coman, C., Țiru, L. G., Meseșan-Schmitz, L., Stanciu, C., & Bularca, M. C. (2020). Online Teaching and Learning in Higher Education during the Coronavirus Pandemic: Students' Perspective. *Sustainability*, 12(24), 10367. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su122410367>
- Demir Kaymak, Z., & Horzum, M. B. (2013). Relationship between Online Learning Readiness and Structure and Interaction of Online Learning Students. *Educational Sciences: Theory & Practice*. <https://doi.org/10.12738/estp.2013.3.1580>
- Dziuban, C., Moskal, P., Thompson, J., Kramer, L., DeCantis, G., & Hermsdorfer, A. (2015). Student Satisfaction with Online Learning: Is it a Psychological Contract? *Online Learning*, 19(2). <https://doi.org/10.24059/olj.v19i2.496>
- Engin, M. (2017). Analysis of Students' Online Learning Readiness Based on Their Emotional Intelligence Level. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 5(12A), 32–40. <https://doi.org/10.13189/ujer.2017.051306>
- Ergogo, A. (2012). Factors Influencing Students' Learning of Mathematics: The Case of First Cycle Secondary Schools in Hadiya Zone [Masters, Addis Ababa University]. <http://thesisbank.jhia.ac.ke/9523/>
- Eshun, B. (2006). Sex-differences in attitude of students towards Mathematics in secondary schools. *Mathematics Connection*, 4. <https://doi.org/10.4314/mc.v4i1.21495>
- Felix, U. (2001). A multivariate analysis of students' experience of web based learning. *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*, 17(1), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.14742/ajet.1770>
- Harahap, M., Pristiyono, P., Lubis, J., Ikhlah, M., & Anjar, A. (2021). Level of Satisfaction of Online Learning in Mediation Lecturer Competence on Learning Motivation. *Budapest International Research and Critics Institute (BIRCI-Journal): Humanities and Social Sciences*, 4(3), 3981–3990. <https://doi.org/10.33258/birci.v4i3.2166>
- Harman, G., & Çelikler, D. (2012). A Review Study About Important Of Readiness in Education. 10.
- Hayes, A. F. (2018). *Introduction to Mediation, Moderation, and Conditional Process Analysis*. 527.
- Herguner, G., Son, S. B., Herguner Son, S., & Donmez, A. (2020). The Effect of Online Learning Attitudes of University Students on Their Online Learning Readiness. *Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology-TOJET*, 19(4), 102-110.
- Hergüner, G., Son, S. B., Son, S. H., & Dönmez, A. (2020). The Effect of Online Learning Attitudes of University Students on their Online Learning Readiness. *The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology*, 19(4), 9.
- Holmes, B., & Gardner, J. (2006). *e-Learning: Concepts and Practice*. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781446212585>

- Horzum, M. B. (2017). Interaction, Structure, Social Presence, and Satisfaction in Online Learning. *EURASIA Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 11(3). <https://doi.org/10.12973/eurasia.2014.1324a>
- Horzum, M. B., Kaymak, Z. D., & Gungoren, O. C. (2015). Structural Equation Modeling Towards Online Learning Readiness, Academic Motivations, and Perceived Learning. *Educational Sciences: Theory & Practice*. <https://doi.org/10.12738/estp.2015.3.2410>
- Hung, M.-L., Chou, C., Chen, C.-H., & Own, Z.-Y. (2010). Learner readiness for online learning: Scale development and student perceptions. *Computers & Education*, 55(3), 1080–1090. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2010.05.004>
- Karatas, S., & Simsek, N. (2009). Comparisons of Internet-Based and Face-to-Face Learning Systems Based on “Equivalency of Experiences” According to Students’ Academic Achievements and Satisfactions. *Quarterly Review of Distance Education*, 10(1), 65–74.
- Lau, C. C. Y. (2008). Effects of Personal Characteristics on Learner Online Learning Readiness. 16.
- Lau. (2012). The impacts of personal qualities on online learning readiness at Curtin Sarawak Malaysia (CSM). *Educational Research and Reviews*, 7(20). <https://doi.org/10.5897/ERR09.229>
- Lee, J. (2014). An exploratory study of effective online learning: Assessing satisfaction levels of graduate students of mathematics education associated with human and design factors of an online course. *The International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 15(1). <https://doi.org/10.19173/irrodl.v15i1.1638>
- MacKinnon, D. P. (2012). *Introduction to Statistical Mediation Analysis* (1st ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203809556>
- Moss G (1987). *The trainers handbook*. Singapore: Singapore Institute of Management
- Muasyaroh, H., & Royanto, L. R. M. (2021). Pembelajaran jarak jauh di masa pandemi COVID-19: Peran literasi digital dan task value terhadap self-regulated learning mahasiswa. *Jurnal Psikologi Ulayat*, 8(2), 247–265. <https://doi.org/10.24854/jpu172>
- Panattil, S. J., George, A., Joy, M. M., Panattil, S. J., George, A., & Joy, M. M. (1 C.E., January 1). A View on the Impact of Gamified Services in the Wake of the COVID-19 Pandemic: An Interdisciplinary Approach (a-view-on-the-impact-of-gamified-services-in-the-wake-of-the-covid-19-pandemic) [Chapter]. <https://Services.Igi-Global.Com/Resolvedoi/Resolve.aspx?Doi=10.4018/978-1-7998-9223-6.Ch005>; IGI Global. <https://www.igi-global.com/gateway/chapter/www.igi-global.com/gateway/chapter/296442>
- Pavan Kumar, S. (2021). Impact of Online Learning Readiness on Students Satisfaction in Higher Educational Institutions. *Journal of Engineering Education Transformations*, 34(0), 64. <https://doi.org/10.16920/jeet/2021/v34i0/157107>
- Prasetio, A. P., Azis, E., Fadhillah, D. D., & Fauziah, A. F. (2017). Lecturers’ Professional Competency and Students’ Academic Performance in Indonesia Higher Education. *International Journal of Human Resource Studies*, 7(1). <https://doi.org/10.5296/ijhrs.v7i1.10902>
- Rafsanjani, M. A., Pamungkas, H. P., Laily, N., & Prabowo, A. E. (2021). Online Learning During the Covid-19 Pandemic: Readiness and Satisfaction among Indonesian Students. *Center for Educational Policy Studies Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.26529/cepsj.1113>
- Rizki Mulyani, S., Ramadhanu, A., Permata Sari, D., Husna Arsyah, R., & Sri Wahyuni Nengsih, N. (2019). Convergence Analysis of Acceleration and Generalization of E-Learning in the Manifestation of Globalization Education Readiness 4.0. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1339(1), 012078. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1339/1/012078>
- Robbins, S. P., & Judge, T. A., Organizational culture. *Organizational behavior*, 28-50, (2007)
- Rucker, D. D., Preacher, K. J., Tormala, Z. L., & Petty, R. E. (2011). Mediation Analysis in Social Psychology: Current Practices and New Recommendations. *Social and Personality Psychology Compass*, 5(6), 359–371. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1751-9004.2011.00355.x>
- Sedgwick, P. (2012). Pearson’s correlation coefficient. *BMJ*, 345(jul04 1), e4483–e4483. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.e4483>
- Shrout, P. E., & Bolger, N. (2002). Mediation in experimental and nonexperimental studies: New procedures and recommendations. *Psychological Methods*, 7(4), 422–445. <https://doi.org/10.1037/1082-989X.7.4.422>
- Simonson, M., Smaldino, S., Albright, M., & Zvacek, S. (2000). *Teaching and Learning at a Distance: Foundations of Distance Education*. Merrill/Prentice Hall, Upper Saddle River, NJ 07458, Web site: <http://www.prenhall.com/simonson> (\$38). Interactive study guides and PowerPoint presentations available at: <http://www.prenhall.com/simonson>. Set of 11 videos illustrating concepts in practice available from: Association for Educational Communications and Technology (AECT), 1025 Vermont Ave. NW, Suite 820, Washington, DC 20005, Tel: 202-347-7839. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED445216>
- Tapia, M., & Marsh, G. (2002). CONFIRMATORY FACTOR ANALYSIS OF THE ATTITUDES TOWARD MATHEMATICS INVENTORY. 14.

Tobias, S. (1995). *Overcoming math anxiety*. New York, NY: W. W. Norton

Topal, A. D. (2016). Examination of University Students' Level of Satisfaction and Readiness for E-Courses and the Relationship between Them. *European Journal of Contemporary Education*, 15(1). <https://doi.org/10.13187/ejced.2016.15.7>

Wei, H.C., & Chou, C. (2020). Online learning performance and satisfaction: Do perceptions and readiness matter? *Distance Education*, 41(1), 48–69. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01587919.2020.1724768>

Yilmaz, R. (2017). Exploring the role of e-learning readiness on student satisfaction and motivation in flipped classroom. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 70, 251–260. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2016.12.085>

Zan, R., & Di Martino, P. (2007). Attitude toward mathematics: Overcoming the positive/negative dichotomy. *Montana Council of Teachers of Mathematics*, 3, 157–168.

Zhao, X., Lynch, J. G., Jr., & Chen, Q. (2010). Reconsidering Baron and Kenny: Myths and Truths about Mediation Analysis. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 37(2), 197–206. <https://doi.org/10.1086/651257>

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